

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18980002](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18980002)

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Single Event Effects Characterization for TriglaV: Radiation-tolerant SoC for High Energy Physics Experiments</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA13-437</i>
General application	<i>High-energy Physics Accelerator/Detectors</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Anvesh Nookala, CERN</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Marco Andorno, CERN Benoit Denking, CERN</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>08.09.2025</i>
Facility	<i>HIF of Cyclotron, UCLouvain</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>12h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The TriglaV ASIC is the first fault-tolerant System-on-Chip (SoC) implemented in 28 nm bulk CMOS intended to demonstrate reliable operation in the harshest radiation environments of High-Energy Physics (HEP) experiments. Its core components are a micro-controller class RISC-V processor, 64 KiB of SRAM, interconnects and common peripherals such as UART, I2C and JTAG. Radiation hardness is achieved by extensive application of triplication or ECC of digital logic alongside layout-level techniques to ensure tolerance against SEE. Additionally, the inherent tolerance of the 28 nm bulk CMOS process to TID accumulation expected in HEP experiments is leveraged. Error counting, debug features, configurable booting and operating parameters are included to further study radiation-induced effects in SoC architectures. Irradiation results are intended to study SEE rates, possible failures. The longer term goal is the establishment of best practices to efficiently integrate radiation-tolerant SoCs into future ASICs for HEP.

<https://radnext.web.cern.ch/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/radnext>

Experiment test report

Figure 1 (Top) Triglav Architecture, (Bottom) 1x2 mm² die image

Triglav Architecture Description

Triglav is microcontroller-class SoC utilizing a triplicated Ibex RV32IMC core with 64 kB ECC-protected SRAM, connected via an Open Bus Interconnect (OBI) crossbar. **Figure 1** shows the various components within the architecture as well as the microscopic die image of the manufactured ASIC. The chip is implemented in TSMC 28nm HPC/RF bulk CMOS technology as part of an MPW. The operating VDD was 0.9 V. The design focuses on mitigation and measurement of Single-Event Effects (SEE):

- Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) applied to almost all logic at the RTL-level using the TMRG tool.
- Fully triplicated combinational and sequential paths, including voter redundancy and feedback-based self-correction.
- Byte-level Hamming (13,8) ECC on all SRAM content as well as data/addr paths in the APB-RT subsystem.
- Development of the MSPU, capable of scrubbing of a full SRAM content within 33 μ s at 250 MHz.
- Bit-interleaved dual-port SRAMs that are robust to Multi-Cell Upsets (MCU) and allow concurrent memory scrubbing and bus access to memory content.
- Formal verification simulation of the triplication applied to the Ibex core and fault injection system simulations.
 - Counting of each individual TMR voting or ECC correction as means to measure SEU cross-section.

Heavy-Ion Irradiation

To measure the sensitivity and reliability of Triglav toward SEEs, a heavy-ion testing campaign was conducted at the Heavy-Ion Facility (HIF) of UCLouvain, Belgium. The chip was irradiated with various ion types representing a Linear Energy Transfer (LET) range from **3.2 to 61.3 MeV cm² mg⁻¹**. The **maximum flux of 1.5e4 ions/s/cm²** was used for all ions alongside a minimum particle fluence of **500e6 ions/cm²** for each ion type. The incidence angle was kept orthogonal to the device. A total

fluence across all ions of 36e8 ions/cm² was reached. Various test programs were applied, operated by an FPGA-based testing harness. Prominently, the embedded CPU benchmark, CoreMark, was continuously executed to actively engage the chip during irradiation. Periodic read-out of SEU counts took place after each program execution.

The corrected SEU cross-section accumulated across all attempted ions and normalized across the total flip-flop count in TriglaV is shown in the **Figure 2**. This cross-section result is of the same order of magnitude as previously reported results obtained for flip-flops of the same 28 nm technology, indicating that, for this circuit, SETs occurring throughout combinatorial logic are not contributing significantly to the overall rate of SEEs.

Figure 2. Per-bit cross-sections for D-Flip-Flops and SRAMs.

The irradiation has shown the strong resilience to SEEs of TriglaV. However, despite the extensive protections against SEEs applied and design verification prior to the tapeout, uncorrected upsets leading to Single-Event Functional Interrupts (SEFI), i.e., program timeouts, memory corruptions or exceptions caught by the CPU, were also observed at high LETs. The SEFI cross-section measured during continuous execution of the CoreMark benchmark is depicted in **Figure 3**. In total, 42 SEFIs were measured across all test program and ions. Currently, there are a variety of potential origins for SEFIs are being investigated, as identifying the causes will be a valuable contribution toward all future ASIC designs for HEP in this technology, let alone SoC circuits. One avenue of study is the potential of Single-event Multi-Transients (SEMT) in combinatorial logic, which can cause TMR majority voting to be insufficient.

Figure 3. System-level SEFI cross-section.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	X
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.